

**Therapeutic Potential of the Siddha Herbo-Mineral Formulation *Mandoorathi Kudineer* in
Anemia and Its Associated Complications**

Dr.K. Harishma ¹, Dr.J.Bhakyalakshmi ², Dr.V.Manjari ³ Dr.R.Madhavan ⁴

^{1,2} PG Scholar, Department of Nanju Maruthuvam, National Institute of Siddha, Tambaram Sanatorium, Chennai

³ Associate Professor, Department of Nanju Maruthuvam, National Institute of Siddha, Tambaram Sanatorium, Chennai

⁴ Head of the Department, Department of Nanju Maruthuvam, National Institute of Siddha, Tambaram Sanatorium, Chennai

Corresponding Author:

Dr.V. Manjari,

Associate Professor, Department of Nanju Maruthuvam,

National Institute of Siddha (Affiliated to TN Dr MGR Medical University, Chennai),

Tambaram Sanatorium.

ABSTRACT:

Anemia is characterized by a decrease in red blood cells or hemoglobin, leading to inadequate oxygen delivery to tissues. Anemia, edema and jaundice are related to each other through various underlying medical conditions. Anemia can lead to edema due to reduced oxygen delivery to tissues, causing fluid buildup and Nutrient deficiencies e.g., iron, vitamin B12 contributing to both anemia and edema. Edema can contribute to jaundice by fluid accumulation in the liver, impairing bilirubin metabolism and excretion. Jaundice can be related to anemia through hemolytic anemia, leading to increased bilirubin levels and liver dysfunction, causing both jaundice and anemia. Treating anemia is an essential part of the overall management plan, especially if it's contributing to jaundice. The indication for *Mandoorathi kudineer* given in the classical texts are anemia, edema and jaundice. This drug review gives the scientific validation for pharmacological action of each drug in the medicine.

KEYWORDS: Anemia, edema, jaundice, *Mandoorathi kudineer*

1 INTRODUCTION:

According to the World Health Organization, anaemia is characterized by a reduction in the number of red blood cells or a decline in their ability to transport oxygen, resulting in an inadequate supply to meet the body's physiological needs. Globally, it is estimated that about 1.6 billion individuals are affected, primarily due to poor nutritional intake [1]. Nearly 56% of adolescent girls and about 30% of adolescent boys are reported to be anaemic. In most cases, particularly among women, the condition arises from mild to severe iron deficiency [2].

In cases of severe anaemia, the diminished ability of the blood to transport oxygen results in inadequate oxygen supply to the tissues, causing hypoxia. This can cause capillary leak, allowing fluid to leak into the interstitial space, causing edema. Sometimes, iron deficiency anemia coexists with protein malnutrition (especially in children), and Chronic, severe anemia may lead to high-output cardiac failure, which can eventually lead to congestive heart failure, resulting in peripheral and pulmonary edema. Edema occurs in around 10-30% of patients with anemia when it coexists with kidney or heart disease [3].

Chronic liver disease (CLD), irrespective of its underlying cause, is often accompanied by hematological disturbances, with anemia being one of the most common, affecting nearly 75% of individuals with advanced disease. In cirrhosis, the development of anemia is usually multifactorial and arises from diverse mechanisms. Therefore, addressing anemia forms an important component of comprehensive management, particularly when it plays a role in worsening jaundice [4].

Siddha system of medicine has many medicines for anemia and its complications. One such medicine *Mandoorathi kudineer*, is widely used for treating anemia, edema and jaundice [5]. This drug review gives the scientific validation for pharmacological action of each drug in the medicine.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

The information was gathered through a comprehensive search across multiple electronic databases, such as Google Scholar, PubMed, Wiley, ScienceDirect, ACS Publications, SpringerLink, Semantic Scholar, and Embase, using keywords such as “*Mandooram*”, “Ferroso ferric oxide”, “*Mangifera indica*”, “*Hydrophila auriculate*”, “*Phyllanthus amarus*”, “*Eclipta prostata*”, “*Cuminum cyminum*”, “Pharmacological activity,” “Hepatoprotective activity,” “Antioxidant”, “Anti-inflammatory”, “Nephroprotective” along with their combinations. Special emphasis was placed on keywords related to pharmacological actions, ethnopharmacology, traditional medicine, Siddha, and herbal medicine. The data collected primarily covered the period from 2019 to 2025, and the analysis took about six months.

Articles were selected based on their direct relevance to the composition of *Mandoorathi Kudineer* and its therapeutic uses, along with the availability of full-text access and study types, including clinical trials, mechanistic investigations, and review papers. Exclusion criteria included duplicate publications, studies lacking methodological rigor, or those unrelated to the research focus. Works that did not address treatment aspects or were not directly applicable to the topic were also left out. The process involved a stepwise approach: initial screening of titles and abstracts, followed by detailed review of full texts, and the application of inclusion and exclusion standards. This ensured that only well-designed and relevant studies were incorporated,

contributing valuable evidence on the effectiveness of *Mandoorathi Kudineer* in treating Vatha diseases.

2.2 INGREDIENTS OF THE MEDICINE:

- Purified *Mandooram* (Ferroso ferric oxide)
- *Maavilai* (*Mangifera indica* Linn)
- *Neermulli* (*Hydrophila auriculate* (K. Schum) Heine)
- *Keezhanelli* (*Phyllanthus amarus* Lin. Schum. & Thonn)
- *Karisalai* (*Eclipta prostrata* Linn)
- *Seeragam* (*Cuminum Cyminum* Linn)
- *Neer* (water)

2.3 PURIFICATION:

2.3.1 MANDOORAM (Ferroso ferric oxide):

1. Mix the pulverised *Kittam* (1 part), Tamarind leaf (4 parts), and water (8 parts) together and boil this for 3 hours. On cooling, rinse it off well, dry it, and winnow away the tamarind leaf from it. Triturate the *Kittam* powder and burn it with 8 volumes of cow's urine. Finally, rinse it off well once all the urine has evaporated [6].
2. Soak the *Ayakitta* powder in Grape fermented liquid (*Thiraatchai Kaadi*) for 2 weeks and then soak it in garlic (*Allium sativum*) extract for one week. Roast this with almond oil or cow's ghee and pulverize it to a fine powder to get the purified form [7].

2.3.2 CUMINUM CYMINUM

- Soak the *Cuminum cyminum* in lime stone water for 3 hours (1 Saamam) and dry it to get the purified form [8].
- Dry the *Cuminum cyminum* in sunlight for 6 hours and roast it slightly [9].

2.4 INDICATIONS:

- Paandu (Anaemia)

- Sobai (edema)
- Kaamalai (Jaundice) [5, 10]

2.5 ADMINISTRATION

Orally, BD

DOSE: 30-60 ml [5, 6]

3 LITERATURE REVIEW:

TABLE -1 DRUG PROFILE OF MANDOORATHI KUDINEER:

S. N O	DRUG	SCIENTIFIC NAME	TASTE	POTENCY	DIVISION	ACTION
1.	<i>Mandooram</i>	<i>Ferroso ferric oxide</i>	Astringent, mild sour, bitter	hot	pungent	Nutritive, stomachic, alterative, haemopoietic [7]
2.	<i>Maavilai</i>	<i>Mangifera indica</i> Linn	Astringent	hot	pungent	Astringent [11]
3.	<i>Neermulli</i>	<i>Hygrophila auriculate</i> (K. Schum) Heine	sweet, slight bitter	cold	sweet	demulcent, diuretic, tonic, refrigerant [11]
4.	<i>Seeragam</i>	<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> Linn	pungent, sweet	cold	sweet	Astringent, stomachic, stimulant, carminative [11]
5.	<i>Karisalai</i>	<i>Eclipta prostata</i> Linn	bitter	hot	pungent	cholagogue, tonic, alterative, emetic,

						purgative, hepatic tonic, Deobstruent [11]
6.	<i>keezhanelli</i>	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Lin. Schum. & Thonn	astringent, bitter, sour, sweet	cold	sweet	deobstruent, coolent, diuretic, astringent [11]

TABLE.2: PHARMACOLOGICAL PROFILE OF MANDOORATHI KUDINEER:

S.N O	SCIENTIFI C NAME	FAMILY	PHARMACOLOGICAL COMPOSITION	NUTRITIONAL COMPOSITION
1.	<i>Ferroso ferric oxide</i>	-	-	-
2.	<i>Mangifera indica</i> Linn	Anacardiaceae	Catechin, Epigallocatechin gallate, Elemene, Humulene, Linalool, Mangiferin, Quercetin, Isomangiferin, Nerol, Ocimene [12]	potassium (K), phosphorus (P), nitrogen (N), calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), sodium (Na), magnesium (Mg), boron (B), zinc (Zn) manganese (Mn), and vitamins, viz. A, B, E, and C [12]
3.	<i>Hygrophila auriculate</i> (K. Schum) Heine	Acanthaceae	Lupeol, Betulin, Leutolin, Apigenin 7-O-glucoside, Apigenin, 7-O-glucuronide, Stimagsterol, 25-Oxo-hentriacontyl acetate, Methyl 8-n-hexyltetracosanoate [13]	vitamin A, E, C, B1, B2, B5, B6, B7 and B9, Potassium, calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, iron, copper, zinc and manganese [13].

4.	<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> Linn	Apiaceae	cuminlaldehyde, p-cymene, cuminal, α -pinene, and α , β -dihydroxyethylbenzene [14].	potassium (K), calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), sodium (Na), magnesium (Mg), zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu) [14].
5.	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> Linn	Asteraceae	Polyacetylenic thiopenes, Apigenin, Luteolin, Luteolin-7-glucoside, Diosgenin, Tigogenin, Lanosterol, 1-Nonacosanol, Stearic acid, Lacceroic acid dihydroxybenzoic acid, Ecliptasaponin A, B, C & D ,Oleanolic acid, α - amyirin, β - amyirin ,Ursolic acid,Coumarins .Wedelolactone ,Dimethylwedelolactone- 7-glucoside ,Wedelolactone ,Demethylwedelolactone, Isodemethylwedelolactone, Ecliptine ,Nicotine [15].	B, Na, Mg, P, K, Ca, Cr, Mn, Fe, Se, Mo, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn [15]
6	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Lin. Schum. & Thonn	Phyllanthaceae	alkaloids, flavonoids, hydrolysable tannins (Ellagitannins), major lignans (phyllanthin, hypophyllanthin, nirurin niranthin, phylltetralin, niranthin, nirtetralin), polyphenols, triterpenes, sterols and volatile oil [16].	calcium, sodium, magnesium, potassium, copper, zinc, manganese, iron, chromium,molybdenum, selenium,silver, lead, mercury, nickel and cadmium [16]

3.1 PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDY:

3.1.1 MANGIFERA INDICA:

3.1.1.1 HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

The chemopreventive potential of mango pulp extract (MPE) and lupeol was evaluated against liver alterations induced by 7,12-dimethylbenz(a)anthracene (DMBA) in albino Swiss mice. Findings revealed that lupeol/MPE helped protect the liver by regulating cell-growth modulators and mitigating oxidative stress-mediated cellular damage [17].

3.1.1.2 ANTI-ANEMIC ACTIVITY:

Hemolytic anaemia, characterized by a reduction in hematological parameters, was induced in rats through PHZ injection. Oral administration of ethanolic extract of *Mangifera indica* L. leaves at doses of 200 mg and 400 mg was found to significantly elevate hemoglobin levels. Furthermore, inhibition of ROS production in rats was observed, suggesting an antioxidant effect of the extract. These results indicate that *Mangifera indica* L. leaves possess anti-anaemic activity, although further studies are required to elucidate the underlying mechanism of this effect [18].

3.1.1.3 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY:

The anti-inflammatory potential of mango-derived polyphenols, particularly gallic acid and gallotannins, was evaluated using a dextran sodium sulfate (DSS)-induced colitis model in rats. Administration of mango juice resulted in a notable reduction in colon inflammation scores (41%) and cell proliferation indices (38%) during chronic colitis when compared with control juice. Moreover, mango intake significantly downregulated key pro-inflammatory mediators in colonic tissue, including CRP, TNF- α , IL-1 β , GM-CSF, and IL-6. It also inhibited the expression of COX-2, iNOS, and HIF-1 α at both mRNA and protein levels, primarily through modulation of the PI3K (p85 β)/AKT-mTOR signaling pathway via upregulation of miR-126. Further, studies in CCD-18Co cells confirmed the interaction between mango polyphenols, miR-126, and PI3K (p85 β), highlighting a molecular mechanism underlying the protective role of mango against colitis-associated inflammation [19].

The aqueous leaf extract demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory activity in both the cotton pellet granuloma model and carrageenan-induced acute paw edema in rats. In the granuloma pouch test, the inhibition of inflammation was observed as 50.56% with indomethacin, while the extract produced 10.08% inhibition at 200 mg/kg, 28.45% at 500 mg/kg, and 48.72% at 1000 mg/kg. Similarly, in the carrageenan-induced paw edema model, indomethacin (10 mg/kg) achieved 37.5% inhibition, whereas the extract showed 7.5% inhibition at 200 mg/kg, 13.4% at 500 mg/kg, and 36.1% at 1000 mg/kg. These findings suggest a dose-dependent anti-inflammatory effect of the extract, approaching the efficacy of the standard drug at higher concentrations [19].

3.1.1.4 DIURETIC ACTIVITY:

Mangifera indica L. leaf extracts (60% ethanolic and aqueous) contain alkaloids, saponins, tannins, flavonoids, terpenes, and proteins, which contribute to their diuretic effect. Experimental studies demonstrated that doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg significantly increased urine output and promoted sodium and potassium excretion, while chloride excretion remained unaffected. Both extracts, particularly at 400 mg/kg, exhibited notable diuretic activity, with Lipchitz's values indicating 50–65% efficacy compared to furosemide [20].

3.1.1.5 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Extracts of *Mangifera indica* L. 'Irwin', particularly from flowers and old dark green leaves, exhibit strong antioxidant activity through DPPH radical scavenging and SOD-like effects. Pruned mature leaves, often discarded, may serve as a valuable natural source for health supplements and cosmetic applications, though further studies are needed to confirm safety and identify active compounds. [21]

3.1.2 HYGROPHILA AURICULATA:

3.1.2.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

The antioxidant potential of the extract was evaluated through ferric thiocyanate (FTC) and thiobarbituric acid assays. Furthermore, another study demonstrated the hepatoprotective efficacy of the aqueous root extract of *H. spinosa* at an oral dose of 200 mg/kg body weight in rats subjected to CCl₄-induced hepatic injury. Their investigation included the assessment of enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant markers, along with histopathological examinations, to substantiate the hepatoprotective properties of the extract [22].

3.1.2.2 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY:

The ethanolic and aqueous extracts of the plant demonstrated marked anti-inflammatory effects, while the petroleum ether and ethanolic extracts exhibited pronounced analgesic activity. These pharmacological responses, observed in albino rats and mice at an oral dose of 400 mg/kg

body weight, were statistically significant when compared with the respective control groups and were found to be comparable to the standard reference drugs diclofenac sodium and analgin [22].

3.1.2.3 HEMOPOETIC ACTIVITY:

Petroleum ether extract of *Hygrophila auriculata* was found to cause a marked elevation in the white blood cell count. Moreover, a combined extract prepared using petroleum ether and chloroform from the leaves produced a significant increase in erythrocyte count, leukocyte count, and hemoglobin levels [22].

3.1.2.4 DIURETIC ACTIVITY

The diuretic activity was evaluated following the procedure outlined by Lipschitz et al. Male Wistar albino rats weighing 150–200 g was employed for the study. The animals were allocated into groups, with the control group administered normal saline (25 mL/kg body weight, p.o.), while the standard group received frusemide (10 mg/kg, p.o.). The test groups were treated with various extracts or fractions of the plant at a dose of 200 mg/kg, suspended in normal saline. Urine was collected over a period of 5 hours, after which the total urine volume and electrolyte concentrations (Na^+ , K^+ , and Cl^-) were measured. The alcoholic extract of *H. auriculata* (Schum.) Hiene, at 200 mg/kg, produced a significant elevation in urine output along with increased levels of sodium, potassium, and chloride ions, thereby confirming the diuretic potential of the plant [22].

3.1.2.5 HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

For in vitro studies, rat hepatocytes were isolated using a modified Seglen procedure with pentobarbital anesthesia and exposed to CCl_4 (1%) with or without varying concentrations (40–80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of the alkaloid fraction. Hepatocyte necrosis was assessed by measuring alterations in aspartate aminotransferase, alanine aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase, triglycerides, and lactate dehydrogenase. Treatment with the alkaloid fraction significantly restored these biochemical parameters toward normal. Additionally, hepatoprotective activity was confirmed in HepG2 cells exposed to CCl_4 , where a dose-dependent increase in cell viability was observed using the tetrazolium assay. In vivo evaluation in Wistar albino rats (150–200 g) demonstrated that administration of the alkaloid fraction at 80 mg/kg body weight produced hepatoprotective effects

comparable to those of silymarin at 250 mg/kg. The biochemical outcomes were further substantiated by histopathological findings, collectively indicating the strong hepatoprotective efficacy of the alkaloid fraction [23].

3.1.2.6 NEPHROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

The ethanolic extract of the leaves was prepared through Soxhlet extraction using 200 ml of ethanol and 1000 g of powdered leaves, yielding 4.0% w/w extract. Nephroprotection was assessed by monitoring biochemical parameters in serum and tissues. In the disease control group, cisplatin administration led to marked elevations in creatinine, uric acid, SGOT, SGPT, alkaline phosphatase, and BUN, confirming renal impairment. In contrast, rats pre-treated with the extract at doses of 250 and 500 mg/kg (p.o.) exhibited a significant reduction in these biomarkers, demonstrating protective effects. Similarly, in gentamicin- and paracetamol-induced groups, extract pre-treatment at the same doses markedly lowered serum biomarker levels compared with the disease control group, which showed significant increases. These findings suggest that the extract possesses strong nephroprotective activity, likely attributable to its phytoconstituents with established roles in mitigating drug-induced renal damage [23].

3.1.3 CUMINUM CYMINUM:

3.1.3.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Cuminum cyminum exhibits notable antioxidant potential demonstrated through DPPH scavenging, lipid and DNA protection, and inhibition of protein oxidation. Methanolic and aqueous extracts show stronger activity than non-polar extracts, correlating with higher phenolic content. The fruits yield 2.5–4% essential oil, rich in cuminol, though methanolic extracts generally display greater antioxidant activity than the essential oil. These findings highlight *C. cyminum* as a valuable source of natural antioxidants with potential food and therapeutic applications [14].

3.1.3.2 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY:

The aqueous extract of *Cuminum* demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory activity in both acute and chronic models of inflammation. The effect was found to be dose-dependent, with

the maximum reduction of inflammation observed at 200 mg/kg in the acute phase and at 1000 mg/kg in the chronic phase. These findings indicate that the extract possesses potent anti-inflammatory properties, which vary according to the dosage and duration of treatment [24]

3.1.3.3 HEPATOPROTECTIVE AND NEPHROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

Cuminum cyminum seed powder reduces serum levels of alanine and aspartate aminotransferases (ALT and AST) while enhancing the activities of antioxidant enzymes such as catalase (CAT) and peroxidase (POX) in acetaminophen-induced hepatotoxicity models. At 400 mg/kg, the most significant protective effect compared to both lower and higher doses concentrations. Previous research has similarly highlighted the hepatoprotective and antioxidant potential of culinary spices. For instance, El-Ghorab et al. reported cumin and ginger as promising natural sources of antioxidants, while Barakat et al. demonstrated the comparative hepatoprotective efficacy of cumin, ginger, and mustard following five weeks of pre-treatment against acetaminophen-induced hepatic injury [25].

3.1.3.4 TOXICITY STUDIES:

Earlier acute toxicity investigations on *Cuminum cyminum* demonstrated that the extract was well tolerated and considered safe at doses up to 2 g/kg, indicating a wide margin of safety [26].

3.1.4 ECLIPTA PROSTATA: 28

3.1.4.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

The antioxidant potential of *Eclipta prostrata* has been demonstrated in both in vivo and in vitro models. In Sprague–Dawley rats, oral administration of the extract (50–100 mg/kg) significantly reduced oxidative stress markers, including serum lipid peroxides and hydroxyl radicals. In vitro assays further confirmed strong free radical scavenging activity, with the whole-plant extract showing an IC₅₀ of 45.68 µg/mL in the DPPH assay compared to 3.26 µg/mL for ascorbic acid, and potent hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity (IC₅₀: 1.34 µg/mL vs. 1.03 µg/mL for ascorbic acid). The extract also exhibited concentration-dependent ferric reducing power, achieving 75.59% reduction at 250 µg/mL with an IC₅₀ of 100 µg/mL. While these findings

highlight promising antioxidant activity, most studies remain limited to in vitro evaluations, and mechanistic insights are still lacking [27].

3.1.4.2 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY:

Evidence indicates that the methanolic extract of *Eclipta prostrata* exerts anti-inflammatory effects by suppressing NF- κ B activation. This activity is attributed primarily to its coumestan derivatives, including demethylwedelolactone and wedelolactone, which have demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory efficacy in experimental models of acute asthma [28].

3.1.4.3 HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

Several studies have demonstrated the hepatoprotective potential of *Eclipta prostrata* in experimental models of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced hepatotoxicity. Aqueous leaf extracts (250 mg/kg) were shown to significantly reduce elevated serum transaminases and bilirubin levels in rats. Chloroform root extracts and methanolic leaf extracts also exhibited protective effects, with reductions in lysosomal enzyme activity ranging from 47% to 73%, while isolated triterpenoid, alkaloid, saponin, and coumestan fractions produced inhibitory effects of up to 78%. Similarly, ethanolic whole-plant extracts normalized biochemical parameters and restored hepatic enzyme activity disrupted by CCl₄ exposure. Bioactive constituents such as echinocystic acid and eclabasaponin II further demonstrated antiproliferative activity against hepatic stellate cells [29].

3.1.4.4 NEPHROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

Several studies have demonstrated the hepatoprotective potential of *Eclipta prostrata* in experimental models of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced hepatotoxicity. Aqueous leaf extracts (250 mg/kg) were shown to significantly reduce elevated serum transaminases and bilirubin levels in rats. Chloroform root extracts and methanolic leaf extracts also exhibited protective effects, with reductions in lysosomal enzyme activity ranging from 47% to 73%, while isolated triterpenoid, alkaloid, saponin, and coumestan fractions produced inhibitory effects of up to 78%. Similarly, ethanolic whole-plant extracts normalized biochemical parameters and restored hepatic enzyme activity disrupted by CCl₄ exposure. Bioactive constituents such as echinocystic acid and eclabasaponin II further demonstrated antiproliferative activity against hepatic stellate cells [29].

3.1.4.5 TOXICITY STUDIES:

Previous reported acute toxicity evaluation revealed that the median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the AEA was estimated at 1,264 mg/kg for intraperitoneal administration and 3,807 mg/kg for oral administration [30].

3.1.5 PHYLLANTHUS AMARUS:

3.1.5.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Phyllanthus amarus exhibits strong antioxidant activity, demonstrated through various *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies showing free radical scavenging, inhibition of lipid peroxidation, and enhancement of antioxidant enzymes. Its key phytoconstituents, including ellagitannins, flavonoids, and gallic acid derivatives, contribute to these effects. Research highlights its protective role against oxidative stress-related conditions such as liver injury, diabetes, obesity, and toxicity, establishing it as a promising candidate for nutraceutical and therapeutic applications [31].

3.1.5.2 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY:

Research has proved the anti-inflammatory properties of *Phyllanthus amarus* extracts in benzene-induced leukemia models. Treatment with the extract was shown to significantly lower TGF- β levels, indicating its potential role in regulating immune activity, reducing fibrosis, and promoting tissue repair. Interestingly, levels of CRP, IL-8, and TNF- α remained unchanged, suggesting that the extract does not provoke undesirable inflammatory responses. Taken together, these results point to the therapeutic potential of *P. amarus* in controlling benzene-related inflammation and support its possible use as an adjunctive option in leukemia care. However, more detailed mechanistic studies and clinical evaluations are needed to confirm and expand these findings [32].

3.1.5.3 HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY

Research on *Phyllanthus amarus* has demonstrated significant antiviral potential against hepatitis B virus (HBV). In cellular studies using HepG2/C3A cells, the ethanol extract was shown

to inhibit the growth of HBV-infected cells, suggesting a direct suppressive effect on viral proliferation. More recent investigations have expanded this work by assessing its influence on viral entry mechanisms. Specifically, studies with HepG2-NTCP cells measured reductions in HBsAg levels in cell culture supernatants via ELISA, providing experimental support for its role as a candidate in anti-HBV drug development. Complementing these preclinical findings, a clinical evaluation in patients with mild to moderate alcoholic hepatitis revealed that a four-week regimen of *P. amarus* extract conferred therapeutic benefits, thereby highlighting its translational potential from laboratory research to clinical application [31].

Also, studies on *Phyllanthus amarus* have shown its hepatoprotective role against HCV, primarily through enhancing antioxidant activity, reducing lipid peroxidation, and preventing free radical-induced liver damage. In vitro investigations of its ethanol extract, supported by molecular docking, highlighted the potential of key lignans as anti-HCV agents. Furthermore, structure-based analyses identified phyllanthin congeners as potent inhibitors of the HCV NS3 protease, a crucial enzyme in viral replication, underscoring *P. amarus* as a promising candidate for developing novel anti-HCV therapeutics [31].

3.1.5.4 NEPHROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

In previous study, induction of nephrotoxicity in rats using the xenobiotic agent diethylnitrosamine (DEN) resulted in significant elevations of kidney function markers. However, concurrent administration of *Phyllanthus amarus* markedly modulated these parameters and protected against DEN-induced renal tissue damage. The protective effect is attributed to attenuation of oxidative stress and enhancement of the antioxidant defense system, consistent with earlier findings on other plant extracts with strong antioxidant activity. Treatment with *P. amarus* leaves significantly restored altered kidney function indices, including urea, creatinine, sodium, potassium, and chloride, thereby demonstrating its ability to counteract DEN-induced renal toxicity [33].

3.1.5.5 EFFECT ON HEMATOLOGICAL PARAMETERS

In benzene-induced leukemia models, *Phyllanthus amarus* extracts showed distinct effects on blood parameters. The methanolic extract improved red blood cell indices, suggesting benefits

against anemia, while the ethanol extract modulated white blood cell counts, indicating immune effects. However, all extracts prolonged clotting times, highlighting a potential risk of bleeding complications [31].

3.1.5.6 TOXICITY STUDIES:

Toxicological evaluations of *Phyllanthus amarus* have demonstrated its safety at oral doses of 1000, 1500, and 2000 mg/kg body weight administered daily for two weeks in albino rats. No overt signs of toxicity, significant alterations in body or organ weights, renal function, or histopathological changes were observed, indicating a favorable safety profile. Moreover, the herb enhanced *in vivo* antioxidant defenses while reducing malondialdehyde levels, further supporting its non-toxic nature and therapeutic potential [34].

A sub-chronic toxicity assessment revealed that the median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the crude ethanolic leaf extract of *Phyllanthus amarus* exceeds 5000 mg/kg, while the effective dose (ED₅₀) was determined to be 200 mg/kg, yielding a therapeutic index of 25. These results indicate a wide margin of safety and strong pharmacological efficacy, with no evidence of toxicity at therapeutic levels. The findings support the conclusion that *P. amarus* is both safe and non-toxic in experimental mice, consistent with earlier reports in the literature [34, 35].

4 DISCUSSION:

Although economic progress has improved living standards, anaemia remains prevalent in many communities, largely due to malnutrition and the increasing shift from traditional nutritious diets to processed and junk foods. In Siddha medicine, the condition is referred to as *Pandu*, a term derived from the story of King Pandu, the father of the Pancha Pandavas. The word itself denotes paleness or whitish discoloration, reflecting the classical signs of anaemia such as pallor of the skin, eyes, and tongue [2].

When severe, chronic anaemia is accompanied by oedema, it is often associated with salt and water retention, decreased renal blood flow, reduced glomerular filtration, and neurohormonal activation—mechanisms comparable to those observed in oedema caused by cardiac disease. However, unlike heart disease, anaemia is typically marked by high cardiac output, reduced systemic vascular resistance, and low blood pressure. This is thought to occur because the low

haemoglobin concentration fails to adequately regulate endothelium-derived relaxing factor, leading to generalized vasodilation. The resulting drop in blood pressure is considered to stimulate neurohormonal pathways, ultimately causing salt and water retention [3].

Anaemia and liver disease are closely linked, and one can influence the development or worsening of the other. anaemia itself can contribute to liver dysfunction. Hemolytic anaemias (e.g., sickle cell disease, thalassemia): Chronic breakdown of red blood cells leads to iron overload, which can damage the liver. Iron overload syndromes (e.g., hemochromatosis): Excess iron from repeated transfusions can deposit in the liver, leading to fibrosis or cirrhosis [4].

The Siddha system, which emphasizes the concept of food as medicine, has also provided well-structured treatment guidelines for anemia [36]. The Siddhars, with their profound insights, prescribed formulations comprising herbs, herbo-mineral preparations, and metallic compounds that are naturally rich in essential micro- and macronutrients such as calcium, vitamin C, zinc, and iron [37]. Among the metallic ingredients, various forms of iron—including ferrous sulfate, magnetite, and iron rust—were predominantly employed. These substances were carefully selected, purified, and processed through traditional methods that later evolved into standardized operating procedures. Importantly, the form of iron present in the final preparation is predominantly ferrous, which is known to enhance pharmacokinetic properties and improve bioavailability.

One such classical formulation is *Mandoorathi Kudineer*, a decoction. The aggregated particles in this decoction play a crucial role in enhancing the absorption of active principles through multiple mechanisms, making it more effective than many other dosage forms. According to Siddha principles, anaemia and liver disorders are attributed to deranged *pitham*, while edema arises from disturbances in *kabham* and *vatham* [38]. The ingredients of *Mandoorathi Kudineer* possess predominantly sweet and pungent tastes, which regulate *vatham* and *kabham*, and more importantly restore the balance of *pitham* [39 - 42]. This unique property makes it a preferred Siddha medicine for the management of anaemia and its related complications.

5 CONCLUSION:

The findings suggest that natural iron-rich compounds, particularly those derived from certain plants and metals in the composition of *Mandoorathi kudineer* may have a beneficial role in

managing iron deficiency anemia. This medicine may offer a complementary approach to traditional iron supplements, potentially improving treatment outcomes and reducing side effects. Further studies are warranted to investigate the efficacy and safety of these natural compounds in managing iron deficiency anemia and related disorders.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the support and facilities provided by the National Institute of Siddha, Tambaram Sanatorium.

FUNDING

The author(s) received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization: KH; Methodology, Data collection and compilation, Manuscript Writing: KH, JB; Proofreading and editing: KH, JB, VM, RM.

REFERENCE:

1. Guideline on haemoglobin cutoffs to define anaemia in individuals and populations [Internet]. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2024. Background. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK602200/>
2. Chakrabarty M, Singh A, Singh S, Chowdhury S. Is the burden of anaemia among Indian adolescent women increasing? Evidence from Indian Demographic and Health Surveys (2015-21). *PLOS Glob Public Health*. 2023 Sep 6;3(9):e0002117. doi: 10.1371/journal.pgph.0002117. PMID: 37672528; PMCID: PMC10482272.
3. Obeagu EI, Obeagu GU. Anemia and cerebrovascular disease: pathophysiological insights and clinical implications. *Ann Med Surg (Lond)*. 2025 May 21;87(6):3254-3267. doi: 10.1097/MS9.0000000000002907. PMID: 40486649; PMCID: PMC12140788.

4. Sharma P, Goyal NK, Agarwal S, Kumar K, Mittal A, Raghava M. Haematological Abnormalities in Chronic Liver Disease. *Journal of Heart Valve Disease*. 2025 Mar;30(3):123-133.
5. Mandoorathi Kudineer
6. The Siddha formulary of India, Part – 1, Edition – 1, 1992, Government of India Ministry of Health and Family Welfare
7. Thiagarajan R. Gunapadam thathu – Jeeva vaguppu. Vol. 1. 1st ed. Chennai: Indian Medicine and Homeopathy Department; 2009.
8. R. C. Mohan, Yagobu vaithiyam 300, Thamarai Noolagam, Chennai.
9. I Sornamariyamal. Sarakku suthi Seimurai, Amudha Nilayam, 2012, Chennai.
10. Sambasivam Pillai TV. Tamil Dictionary. Vol. 1–5. 4th ed. Chennai: Tamil Nadu Siddha Medical Council; 1992.
11. Thiagarajan R. Gunapadam Mooligai Part 1. Chennai: Indian Medicine and Homeopathy Department; 2013.
12. Kumar M, Saurabh V, Tomar M, Hasan M, Changan S, Sasi M, Maheshwari C, Prajapati U, Singh S, Prajapat RK, Dhumal S, Punia S, Amarowicz R, Mekhemar M. Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) Leaves: Nutritional Composition, Phytochemical Profile, and Health-Promoting Bioactivities. *Antioxidants (Basel)*. 2021 Feb 16;10(2):299. doi: 10.3390/antiox10020299. PMID: 33669341; PMCID: PMC7920260.
13. Deepika Ekambaram and K. S. Santhy, Phytochemical Characterization and Assessment of *Hygrophila auriculata* (Buch. -Ham) Leaves for Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activity, *Indian J Pharm Sci* 2023;85(2):501-510; doi - 10.36468/pharmaceutical-sciences.1116
14. Singh N, Yadav SS, Kumar S, Narashiman B. A review on traditional uses, phytochemistry, pharmacology, and clinical research of dietary spice *Cuminum cyminum* L. *Phytother Res*. 2021;35(9):5007-5030. doi:10.1002/ptr.7133
15. Timalcina D, Devkota HP. *Eclipta prostrata* (L.) L. (Asteraceae): Ethnomedicinal Uses, Chemical Constituents, and Biological Activities. *Biomolecules*. 2021 Nov 22;11(11):1738. doi: 10.3390/biom11111738. PMID: 34827736; PMCID: PMC8615741.

16. FALOYE T, OLADUNMOYE M, OMOYA F, AJAYI K. Evaluation of Phytochemicals, Mineral Compositions and Nutritional Value Present in *Phyllanthus amarus* Leaves (Schum. and Thonn). *Journal of Applied Sciences & Environmental Management*. 2025 Jul 1;29(7).
17. Sivaranjini S, Sakthi Abirami M, Arun K, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research Human*, 2024; Vol. 30 (8): 144-157.
<https://ijpr.humanjournals.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/10.Sivaranjini.S-Sakthi-Abirami.M.pdf>
18. Samanta, Subhasis & Chanda, Ranabir & Banerjee, Janmajoy. Studies on the antidiabetic effects of ethanolic extract of leaves of *Mangifera indica*, 2020, 12 (11); 124 – 129.
19. Al-Snafi, Ali & Talab, Tayseer. A review on components and pharmacology of *Mangifera indica*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2021, 13 10.31838/ijpr/2021.13.02.405.
20. Abhishek R. Bural, Rushikesh S. Wandhekar and Omkar S, Zarekar, Study Diuretic Action of Leaves of *Mangifera Indica*, *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2018, 7(14), 931-934.
21. Itoh K, Matsukawa T, Okamoto M, Minami K, Tomohiro N, Shimizu K, Kajiyama SI, Endo Y, Matsuda H, Shigeoka S. In vitro antioxidant activity of *Mangifera indica* leaf extracts. *Journal of Plant Studies*; Vol. 2020 Dec 14;9(2).
22. Walkunde Anushka, Datkhile Sachin , Dere Omkar , Gadage Shubham , Shingote Kishori, A Review on Pharmacognostic and Pharmacological Activities of *Hygrophila Auriculata*, *Journal For Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, <https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2023.50357>
23. Shraddha M. Parab, Nikita B. Parab , Priyesh L. Panchal, Pranay P. Palkar, Vijay A Jagtap, review on pharmacological activities of *hygrophila auriculata*, *International Journal of Scientific Development and Research*, 2024 9 (6)
24. Golabi S, Mohammadi A, Chamkouri N. Investigation of Anti-inflammatory Effect of Aqueous Extract of *Cuminum cyminum* L. by Formalin Inflammatory Model in Male Rats. *J. Med. Plants* 2019; 18 (72) :236-246
URL: <http://jmp.ir/article-1-2318-en.html>

25. Mozafari A, Gol A, Mohammadzadeh A. Hepatoprotective properties of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds powder as post-treatment for acetaminophen-induced acute hepatic injury. *J Adv Med Biomed Res.* 2023; 31(145): 170-6.
26. Kaur, Ginpreet, Upadhyay, Nidhi, Tharappel, Leo J Philip and Invally, Mihir. "Pharmacodynamic interaction of cumin seeds (*Cuminum cyminum* L.) with glyburide in diabetes" *Journal of Complementary and Integrative Medicine*, vol. 16, no. 4, 2019, pp. 20180080. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jcim-2018-0080>
27. Rashid, M. H. O., Das, J. R. ., Akter, A. ., Uddin, J. ., Parvin, N. ., Laboni, F. R. ., ... Karim, N. . (2022). Possible Role of Phenolics and Flavonoids in Antioxidant, Cytotoxic and Thrombolytic Activities of *Eclipta prostrata* L. *Bangladesh Pharmaceutical Journal*, 25(2), 164–174. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bpj.v25i2.60967>
28. Shakil M, Islam MS, Rashid SB, Islam S, Akter A, Mysha NT, Haider Z, Jannat B, Tasnim S, Ahmed MH, Azim S. Bioactivity Assessment of Analgesic and Anti-inflammatory Properties of *Eclipta prostrata* Extract on Rat Models. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports.* 2025 May 15;19(5):226-36.
29. Timalsina D, Devkota HP. *Eclipta prostrata* (L.) L. (Asteraceae): Ethnomedicinal Uses, Chemical Constituents, and Biological Activities. *Biomolecules.* 2021; 11(11):1738. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom11111738>
30. Adegoke et al.; *J. Adv. Med. Pharm. Sci.*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 9-22, 2024; Article no.JAMPS.111310
31. Bose Mazumdar Ghosh, A., Banerjee, A. & Chattopadhyay, S. An insight into the potent medicinal plant *Phyllanthus amarus* Schum. and Thonn. *Nucleus* **65**, 437–472 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13237-022-00409-z>
32. Anyiam AF, Muhibi MA, Iyare GI, Omosigho PO, Olaniyan MF, Obi E, Arinze-Anyiam OC, Emmanuel FO, Rachel OO, Obeagu EI, Eze U. Anti-inflammatory Effects of *Phyllanthus amarus* Extracts Against Benzene-Induced Leukemia in Rats. *Avicenna Journal of Medical Biochemistry.* 2024 Dec 31;12(2):114-22.
33. Yakubu OE, Bando DC, Zephaniah M, Umaru IJ, Abu MS. Kidney function status of Wistar rat treated with ethanolic extract of *Phyllanthus amarus* leaves owing to diethylnitrosamine intoxication. *Asian Journal of Tropical Biotechnology.* 2022 May 3;19(1).

34. Dennis KE, Bridget K, Stanislaus OC. Study of Subacute Toxicity in Wistar Rats Challenged with *Phyllanthus amarus* Schum and Thonn. *Journal of Complementary and Alternative Medical Research*. 2024 Aug 5;25(8):36-46.
35. Adolor OE, Onyesom I, Opajobi AO, Mordi JC. Evaluation of median lethal dose and subchronic oral toxicity assessment of ethanolic leaf extract of *Phyllanthus amarus*. *J Pharm Res Int*. 2019 Apr;26(4):1-8.
36. Achikanu, Ujah, and MO Ezenwali, Mineral Content of *Phyllanthus amarus* CE, *IOSR Journal Of Pharmacy And Biological Sciences (IOSR-JPBS)* 17 (6) Ser. IV, 2022; PP 01-05 DOI: 10.9790/3008-1706040105
37. Kumar, A. Rajendra1; Gunalan, Gayathri; Firdouse, K. Hina; Archana, A Evidence-based Clinical Efficacy of Certain Indigenous Traditional Siddha Formulations in Combating Anemia: A Global Health Burden – A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Health Care* 15(4):p 374-384, Oct–Dec 2023. | DOI: 10.4103/ajprhc.ajprhc_83_23
38. Raghavi M, Abarna B, Adithya RS, Madhavan R. Therapeutic efficacy of Ashtabhairava mathirai in fever management: A review. *Int J Res Ayurveda Pharm*. 2024;15(4):150–4. doi:10.7897/2277-4343.154138
39. K.N.K. Mudhaliyar, In: *Siddha Maruthuvam (Podhu)*. Department of Indian Medicine and Homoeopathy; 2004.Chennai, Tamil Nadu.
40. Venugopal PM. *Udal thathuvam*. Chennai: Indian Medicine and Homeopathy Department; 2013.
<http://www.tamildigitallibrary.in/book-detail.php?id=jZY9lup2kZl6TuXGlZQdjZY6kZly>
41. M. Shanmugavelu, *Noi nadal Noi Mudhal Nadal Thirattu, Part – 1*, Department of Indian Medicine and Homoeopathy; 2004.Chennai, Tamil Nadu.
https://archive.org/search.php?query=external-identifier%3A%22urn%3Aalcp%3ATVA_BOK_0007017_%E0%AE%A8%E0%AF%8B%E0%AE%AF%E0%AF%8D_%E0%AE%A8%E0%AE%BE%E0%AE%9F%E0%AE%B2%E0%AF%8D_%E0%AE%A8%E0%AF%8B%E0%AE%AF%E0%AF%8D%E0%AE%AE%E0%AF%81%E0%AE%A4%E0%AE%B2%E0%AF%8D_%E0%AE%A8%E0%AE%BE%E0%AE%9F%E0%AE%B2%E0%AF%8D_%E0%AE%A4%E0%AE%BF

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(97\)04223-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(97)04223-2)

42. Subbarayappa BV. Siddha medicine: An overview. *Lancet*. 1997;350(9094):1841–4.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(97\)04223-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(97)04223-2). PMID: 9428267